

Recent advances and future outlooks towards engineered materials and interfaces for PFAS sensing

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ABSTRACT

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are widespread environmental contaminants associated with significant health risks, necessitating sensitive and reliable detection methods across varied matrices. Conventional techniques like liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) provide high sensitivity and specificity but are hampered by their complexity, cost, and limited field applicability. This review critically surveys recent advancements in PFAS sensing, focusing on engineered nanomaterial-based sensors and their integration into practical devices. We categorize sensing materials by structural characteristics, emphasizing nanomaterials functionalized with specific recognition elements to improve selectivity. The review also explores hybrid sensor platforms combining multiple detection modalities. Further, we discuss the role of artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques in enhancing sensor selectivity, data processing, and adaptability to complex environmental samples. Real-world validation studies are analyzed, highlighting sensor performance in matrices including drinking water, serum, and soil, emphasizing strategies to mitigate matrix interferences such as antifouling coatings and sample pretreatment. Challenges in sensor reproducibility, miniaturization, and regulatory compliance for field deployment are also examined. Overall, we provide a comprehensive outlook on the materials innovation, mechanistic understanding, and data-driven approaches that underpin the development of smart, portable PFAS sensors. These advances promise to bridge gaps between laboratory research and real-world applications, supporting regulatory monitoring and environmental protection efforts with scalable, cost-effective sensing solutions.

1. Introduction

PFAS are synthetic chemicals widely used for their stability and surfactant properties in industrial and consumer products. Often referred to as "forever chemicals," they are highly persistent, accumulating globally in groundwater, surface water, soil, and biota. PFAS exposure is linked to significant health risks, including immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption, reproductive toxicity, and cancer. Over 15,000 PFAS compounds have been identified, including long chain legacy compounds such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), as well as short-chain alternatives such as

perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), perfluorononanoic Acid (PFNA), polyfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA), 4,8-dioxo-3H-perfluorononanoic acid (ADONA), perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs) and hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid (HFPO-DA), more commonly known as GenX (<https://www.niehs.nih.gov/health/topics/agents/pfc>. Accessed; PFAS Analytic Tools ECHO). Human exposure occurs primarily through ingestion, dermal absorption, and inhalation (Lewis et al., 2025). Conventional techniques such as liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) are benchmarks for PFAS

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quantification due to their high sensitivity and molecular specificity (Fig. 1) (Kause et al., 2024). Nevertheless, these methods are complex, costly, and dependent on specialized laboratories, limiting their real-time and field deployable. These methods also face challenges detecting non-targeted PFAS and dealing with matrix interferences. Supplementary approaches like the total oxidizable precursor test (TOP) (Antell et al., 2024; Lange et al., 2024), particle-induced gamma emission (PIGE) (Tighe et al., 2021; Ritter et al., 2017), total fluorine (TF), and total organic fluorine (TOF) (Liu et al., 2024; Forster et al., 2023) analyses provide broader fluorine content estimates, though with limited molecular specificity.

Advances in engineered nanomaterials and molecular recognition elements present promising alternatives for PFAS detection. Materials such as nanoparticles, nanotubes, graphene derivatives, MXenes, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), covalent-organic frameworks (COFs), and molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) offer highly tunable surface chemistries and structural features to improve sensitivity and selectivity (Zhang et al., 2025; Cheng et al., 2020). Interface innovations including antifouling coatings and fluorophilic polymer brushes significantly enhance sensor performance in complex water matrices typically prone to organic and surfactant interference. Sensor arrays leveraging pattern recognition tools like principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) have enabled discrimination of structurally similar PFAS such as PFOA, PFOS and GenX (Yu et al., 2024; Sperling et al., 2023). Coupling these arrays with artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) further improves sensor multiplexing, accuracy, and environmental adaptability (Currie et al., 2025; Andraju et al., 2023). ML frameworks incorporating environmental data enable source identification, contamination prediction, and treatment optimization with greater than 90 % classification accuracy (Wang et al., 2024; Fernandez et al., 2023; Cao et al., 2023).

The research on PFAS sensor development has increased with remarkable pace. This is evident from the focused WoS survey done for the keywords ("per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances" OR "PFAS" OR "PFOA" OR "PFOS") AND ("sensor" OR "detection" OR "chemical sensing" OR "biosensor" OR "electrochemical detection"). Publications in this research domain increased from 27 in 2010 to 317 in 2025

(Fig. 2). This review provides a comprehensive, multidimensional perspective on recent PFAS sensor developments, combining bibliometric analysis with mechanistic classification of materials, detailed discussion on recognition elements, application of AI/ML techniques, and practical considerations for sensor translation and commercialization.

Classifying engineered sensing materials by their dimensionality provides an intuitive and practical framework to understand their structural, physicochemical, and sensing properties. It fundamentally influences key material characteristics such as surface area, aspect ratio, electron transport pathways, and accessibility of active sites, all of which critically affect PFAS molecular recognition and signal transduction. However, other factors also importantly modulate sensing efficacy. These include surface chemistry (functional groups, defect sites), material crystallinity, porosity, hybridization with other materials, and integration with device platforms. A comparison of representative reviews in this area given in Table S1, highlights that while prior works have covered aspects of PFAS detection, none have combined a dimensionality-based material classification, recognition-element discussion, AI/ML integration, and a roadmap for translation. This positions our review as a timely and complementary contribution.

2. Conventional methods of PFAS sensing

PFAS detection primarily relies on advanced lab techniques like LC-MS/MS (Androulakakis et al., 2022; Nickerson et al., 2021), GC-MS (Harada et al., 2020), and ion chromatography, known for high sensitivity and specificity. These remain the standard for regulatory monitoring, capable of quantifying PFAS at parts-per-trillion levels in various matrices. However, their complexity, high cost, and reliance on specialized infrastructure limit large-scale and field applications. Complementary methods such as the TOP test (Antell et al., 2024) and PIGE (Tighe et al., 2021), provide broader fluorine quantification but with lower specificity and operational convenience. Despite limitations, traditional methods serve as essential benchmarks for validating emerging PFAS sensor technologies.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the various technologies incorporated in PFAS sensing.

Fig. 2. WoS survey of research articles published from 2010 to 2025 with the keywords ("per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances" OR "PFAS" OR "PFOA" OR "PFOS") AND ("sensor" OR "detection" OR "chemical sensing" OR "biosensor" OR "electrochemical detection").

2.1. PFAS detection using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

LC-MS/MS is the most widely adopted and analytically reliable technique for detecting PFAS in environmental and biological samples due to its high sensitivity, specificity, and molecular resolution. It is considered the gold standard for quantifying legacy PFAS compounds such as perfluorooctanesulfonate (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), as well as emerging short-chain analogs and novel variants like GenX. Typical protocols involve sample preparation through solid-phase extraction (SPE) to concentrate PFAS from complex matrices, followed by reversed-phase chromatography for efficient separation. Electrospray ionization in negative mode coupled with multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) enables selective mass fragmentation and quantification at ultratrace levels, often reaching parts-per-trillion or even lower detection limits. Standardized EPA methods including 533, 537.1, and the ongoing 8327 cover a growing number of PFAS analytes and sample types, including drinking water, wastewater, soil, and biosolids. For example, method 537.1 expands coverage to 40 compounds, addressing both long-chain and short-chain PFAS, and fully supports regulatory compliance and environmental monitoring requirements (O. of R). Recent advancements in LC-MS/MS focus on resolving isomers via optimized fragmentation, improving detection of transformation products, and integrating with nanomaterial-based sample preconcentration to enhance sensitivity and selectivity. For instance, amine-functionalized COFs have been applied for fish tissue PFAS extraction, significantly improving recovery compared to conventional sorbents (Table S2) (Song et al., 2022). Magnetic composites such as Fe₃O₄ enhanced with carbon nanotubes have also been demonstrated to preconcentrate PFAS from water prior to analysis (Song et al., 2023).

Despite its analytical rigor, LC-MS/MS requires sophisticated

instrumentation, intensive sample preparation, and skilled operators, limiting its suitability for routine, real-time, or field-deployable PFAS monitoring. Matrix interferences from salts and organic matter may affect ionization efficiency, necessitating stringent validation for diverse environmental samples. Moreover, limited availability of reference standards for thousands of PFAS analogs reduces comprehensive coverage, prompting the development of high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and suspect/non-target screening workflows. In conclusion, while LC-MS/MS remains indispensable for precise and comprehensive PFAS quantification in regulatory frameworks, ongoing research seeks to streamline workflows, improve throughput, and enable portable alternatives complementing laboratory analysis.

2.2. PFAS detection with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

GC-MS performs a valuable part in the detection of PFAS, particularly in the recognition and assessment of volatile or semi-volatile precursor compounds. Ionic PFAS such as PFOA and PFOS are non-volatile and thermally stable due to which they are not suitable for GC-MS analysis. However, neutral PFAS precursors including fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), fluorotelomer iodides (FTIs) and sulfonamidoalcohols, for example, N-ethyl-N-(2-hydroxyethyl) perfluorooctyl sulfonamide (EtFOSE), N-Methylperfluorooctanesulfonamidoethanol (MeFOSE) can be effectively analyzed using this technique. The volatility of these compounds allows for separation by GC and then detection can be done by MS, often after chemical derivatization which enhances volatility and stability. In one research study UiO-66-NH₂@DES, a magnetic MOF was used in combination with a deep eutectic solvent (DES) to extract perfluoroalkyl iodides (PFAIs) and detected them with GC-MS. The approach demonstrated good sensitivity and MOF recovery.

The relative standard deviation (RSD) varied from 3.00 to 19.4 % and the detection limit was 2.81–34.3 pg/g (Han et al., 2023). Also, a GC-MS technique was developed for identifying and quantifying volatile PFAS in wastewater treatment plant surroundings. FTOHs could not be identified due to their non-ionizability. They optimized column oven temperatures and injection systems using splitless injection at 180 °C and observed improved sensitivity and repeatability. The LOD of the instrument ranged from 0.5 to 2 pg and the method detection limit (MDL) in water was 10 ppt (Dimzon et al., 2017). The method successfully detected compounds such as fluorotelomer olefin, FTIs, fluorotelomer acrylate (FTACs), fluorotelomer methacrylates (FTMACs) and PFAIs, which are easily ionizable by electron impact and chemical ionization. These compounds cannot be ionized by atmospheric pressure chemical ionization or electrospray ionization, limiting the applicability of liquid chromatography for these analytes. Another study introduced a green analytical method coupled with thermal desorption-GC-MS to detect PFCAs within water using stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) (Habib et al., 2024). Using this technique, PFCAs could be detected without the need for derivatization which streamlined the sample preparation process and prevented the use of hazardous chemicals. The LOD of the method was between 21.17 ppt and 73.96 ppt.

Despite the targeted applications, GC-MS is not suitable for routine analysis of ionic PFAS like PFOA, PFOS, PFHxA, or GenX as they have high polarity and thermal lability. Even after derivatization, the decomposition of such species at GC injection temperatures may result in poor recovery or artifact formation. Additionally, the derivatization process itself introduces safety concerns due to the use of reagents like diazomethane which are harmful, leading to workflow complexity. There are also potential derivatization inefficiencies in environmental matrices rich in co-contaminants. Furthermore, in comparison to LC-MS/MS, GC-MS is the less preferred one as LC-MS/MS can assess non-volatile and semi-volatile compounds. Nevertheless, LC-MS/MS comes with its own shortcomings for instance, it has more operational cost and requires more sophisticated operating skills and sample preparation.

To conclude, while GC-MS cannot replace LC-MS/MS in quantifying regulated PFAS in water, it plays a critical role in expanding analytical coverage to neutral precursors. The integration of GC-MS with oxidation protocols and extraction-enhancement platforms enables further awareness of PFAS distribution, transformation and environmental behavior.

The alternative laboratory based analytical techniques have been discussed in the [supplementary information section S2.3](#).

3. Engineered materials for PFAS sensing

Engineered materials offer tailored physicochemical properties for selective, high-affinity PFAS recognition and sensitive signal transduction. Unlike complex, costly mass spectrometry methods, they enable affordable, real-time, portable PFAS monitoring in diverse matrices like water and soil. These materials function via hydrophobic, hydrogen bonding, electrostatic, size exclusion, and fluorophilic interactions. Various nanomaterials, porous frameworks, and imprinting polymers provide structural tunability and signal enhancement. Materials like MIPs, MOFs, and COFs have emerged as robust platforms mimicking biological specificity. Combined with optical, electrochemical, and colorimetric modes, these innovations achieve detection below regulatory levels. Advances in surface chemistry and AI-driven data processing are driving next-generation smart PFAS sensors. A thorough discussion on research studies that incorporated various dimensional nanomaterials has been given in the [supplementary section S3](#).

4. Artificial intelligence and machine learning approaches for PFAS sensing

The integration of AI and ML into PFAS sensor technologies has

transformed monitoring capabilities by improving signal analysis, data interpretation, and pattern recognition. AI/ML techniques excel in handling high-dimensional datasets derived from sensor arrays, spectroscopic systems, and electrochemical impedance measures. These methodologies address key challenges such as noise reduction, selectivity enhancement, and nonlinear signal responses, enabling adaptive, autonomous, and field-deployable sensors. One notable application involved cyclodextrin-mediated nanopore sensors coupled with ML to profile single PFAS molecules, differentiating PFOS and PFOA by analyzing current fluctuations (Table 1) (Wei et al., 2024). This approach enables stochastic signal resolution within complex environmental matrices. In another study, ML algorithms screened over a thousand ionic liquids for the synthesis of an ionic liquid-based molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) achieving over 99 % PFOA removal efficiency (Zhang et al., 2023). Optical sensor advancements include vertically aligned silver nanorod arrays employed as surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) substrates. In toxicity assessment, deep-learning-based image analysis tools quantified neurodevelopmental impacts of various PFAS on nematode models, demonstrating PFAS-driven neuronal activity impairment and motility dysfunction. ML models have also predicted sorption distribution coefficients (K_d) in soils, identifying soil properties (e.g., organic carbon, pH, silt content) that significantly influence PFAS adsorption. Moreover, supervised and unsupervised learning methods such as principal component analysis, artificial neural networks, support vector machines, and random forests have been used to model PFAS uptake and aggregation by plants across multiple species and compounds.

Overall, ML enhances PFAS sensor specificity, sensitivity, and versatility, enabling dynamic calibration, interference compensation, and multiplexed detection. AI/ML integration supports non-targeted PFAS identification and environmental source attribution, critical for linking analytical detection with regulatory decision-making. Challenges persist, primarily concerning the scarcity and heterogeneity of high-quality labeled datasets essential for effective ML training. Synthetic data augmentation and the creation of standardized public databases are emerging strategies to address data limitations. Overfitting remains a risk in ML, mitigated by cross-validation, ensemble models, and robust loss functions; however, ensuring generalizability across diverse PFAS chemistries requires continued research. Practical AI-enabled PFAS sensor deployment demands integration with hardware, edge computation for real-time data preprocessing, and IoT-based networking for high-resolution spatial and temporal monitoring. Operational concerns include power management, cybersecurity, and device maintenance. Collaborative pilot field trials engaging interdisciplinary teams are vital for refining scalable, automated sensing platforms. Automated ML frameworks present promising solutions for on-site adaptive model optimization, ensuring sustained sensor performance post-deployment.

In summary, AI and ML represent paradigm-shifting tools in the PFAS sensing domain, enhancing analytical performance and enabling real-time, multiplexed environmental monitoring. With advancements in data infrastructure and system integration, AI-powered sensors promise to significantly improve PFAS exposure assessment and environmental stewardship.

5. Analytical performance in real-world matrices

The shift of PFAS detection technologies from controlled laboratories to complex environmental and biological matrices poses significant challenges. Real-world matrices such as wastewater, soil leachates, surface and groundwater, biosolids, and biological fluids contain diverse co-contaminants including organic macromolecules and ionic species that interfere with sensor performance. Analytical robustness and matrix tolerance are thus critical metrics for sensor applicability and regulatory acceptance. Recent studies have validated various PFAS sensors in such complex environments. For example, an electrochemical sensor

Table 1
Studies on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning assisted PFAS sensing.

Sr. No.	Target PFAS	Application Domain	ML Technique Used	Key Outcomes	LOD	Advantages of the study	Shortcomings of the study	References
1.	PFOS, PFOA	Nanopore-based single-molecule sensing	Custom ML model for ionic current classification	Differentiated PFAS by chain length and functional groups Built signal database	400 ppt	Enables label-free, single-molecule resolution. Excellent for mixed PFAS.	Requires signal training. Complex hardware. Limited throughput.	Wei et al. (2024)
2.	PFOA	Material design (ionic liquid-MIP)	ML screening of more than 1000 ionic liquids	Identified top-performing ionic liquids for high-affinity MIP synthesis	Adsorption capacity: 5.68×10^5 ppm	Accelerates MIP design Cost-efficient pre-synthesis filtering.	Requires experimental validation. Not a detection system.	Zhang et al. (2023)
3.	11 PFAS (PFOS, PFBS, GenX, etc.)	Neurotoxicity profiling in <i>C. elegans</i>	DeepImageJ (Convolutional neural network based deep learning)	Identified neuron-specific toxicity and behavior changes	0.3–100 ppm exposure range	High-throughput bioimage analysis.	Requires live models. Low throughput for routine sensing.	Currie et al. (2025)
4.	PFOS	Soil sorption modeling	ANN, MLR	Predicted sorption coefficients based on soil parameters (e.g., TOC, pH)	–	Improves transport modeling.	No direct sensing. Dependent on accurate soil property inputs.	Umeh et al. (2021)
5.	19 PFAS across 9 plant species	Plant uptake and accumulation	PCA, ANN, SVM, MLR, RF	Modeled uptake based on compound and plant characteristics	–	Helps identify phytoaccumulators. Scalable modeling	Not a direct detection tool. Output varies by data quality	Adu et al. (2024)

fabricated with nitrogen and boron co-doped carbon nanowalls integrated with molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) via microwave plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition demonstrated reliable detection of PFOS in tap and treated wastewater (Pierpaoli et al., 2023). However, high sulfate content and complexity in landfill leachate hindered accurate quantification. Photo-electrochemical sensors based on TiO₂ nanotube arrays grafted with MIPs showed good recovery and matrix tolerance in river, mountain, and tap waters (Tran et al., 2014). Similarly, AgI-BiOI nanoflake array-based photoelectrochemical MIP sensors provided effective PFAS detection (Gong et al., 2015). Fluorescent sensors such as CdTe/CdS quantum dots functionalized with MIPs exhibited high PFOA removal rates in tap, lake, and river waters, maintaining low relative standard deviation (Zheng et al., 2019). Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) sensors combined with plastic optical fibers and MIPs demonstrated detection of a broad range of PFOA variants, performing comparably to antibody-based devices (Cennamo et al., 2018). A schematic showing the design strategy for a field deployable PFAS sensor has been given in Fig. S5.

Other innovations include phenolic resin-based MIPs with enhanced mass transfer characteristics coupled with LC-MS/MS for trace PFAS detection in food matrices like pork and milk (Ren et al., 2023). Superparamagnetic polydopamine-based MIP nanospheres have been successfully employed for selective PFOS identification and separation from river water, lake water, and human serum samples (Lin et al., 2021). These advancements underscore the importance of developing sensors with high selectivity, sensitivity, and matrix tolerance to enable reliable PFAS detection in real-world applications.

6. Commercialization and translational barriers

Despite notable laboratory progress, translating PFAS sensors into robust, field-ready and commercially viable products remains challenging. Key barriers include sensor reproducibility, scalability, and stability under complex environmental conditions that differ from controlled lab settings. Many sensors show strong analytical performance in synthetic samples but often face diminished sensitivity or signal drift in real waters or soils due to matrix effects, fouling, and variable sample composition. Integrating sensors with power, data processing, and wireless communication is still developing and complicates autonomous deployment.

Commercialization is further hindered by manufacturing inconsistencies, the need for cost-effective mass production, and rigorous regulatory and certification standards. The absence of standardized sensor calibration, validation, and quality control protocols impedes market acceptance. The chemical complexity of PFAS, including numerous homologs and transformation products, demands broad-spectrum, multiplexed sensor designs, increasing complexity and cost. Evolving regulations, with stringent detection limits and compound-specific requirements, often outpace sensor technology readiness. Few PFAS sensors have reached advanced Technology Readiness Levels or market entry. Addressing these gaps requires interdisciplinary collaboration to develop scalable fabrication, harmonized validation, and IoT-enabled monitoring. Long-term field trials and cost-benefit studies remain essential for demonstrating reliability and supporting commercial adoption of PFAS sensing solutions.

7. Summary of results and discussions

The synthesis of engineered nanomaterials, advances in hybrid sensor designs, and AI-powered data analytics collectively represent a paradigm shift in the capability to detect PFAS in complex environmental and biological matrices. Recent studies underscore the superiority of materials such as MXenes and COFs due to their unique physicochemical properties enabling enhanced PFAS binding and sensor response. The integration of multiple sensing mechanisms, such as electrochemical and optical transduction, has addressed limitations inherent to single-modality sensors. Photothermal-colorimetric and photothermal-fluorescent hybrids enable signal amplification and improved selectivity in presence of interfering substances. Colors and fluorescence act as intuitive readouts, whereas electrochemical components provide quantitative data. These multimodal designs represent an evolution toward practical, field-deployable sensors balancing sensitivity with operational simplicity. Machine learning algorithms have enhanced analytical capabilities by improving pattern recognition and interference discrimination in complex sample matrices. Despite data scarcity and standardization challenges, AI models have been successfully trained on augmented datasets to enable adaptive calibration and predictive sensing. This evolution marks a shift from static, threshold-based detection to dynamic and context-aware sensing platforms, critical for real-time environmental monitoring.

8. Conclusion

This review highlights significant advancements in PFAS sensor development, emphasizing engineered nanomaterials and hybrid sensing platforms that enhance sensitivity and selectivity in complex environmental matrices. Materials such as MXenes and COFs offer mechanistic advantages, synergizing conductive, porous, and selective interactions, that underpin ultralow detection limits and improved field applicability. Additionally, the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning facilitates adaptive sensing and robust data interpretation, addressing key challenges in interference mitigation and multiplexed detection. However, significant limitations remain. Laboratory successes often face hurdles in reproducibility, environmental durability, and large-scale manufacturing. Matrix effects and sensor fouling continue to degrade performance in real-world conditions. Furthermore, data scarcity and lack of standardized validation protocols constrain the deployment of AI/ML-powered sensors. Commercial and regulatory barriers hinder widespread adoption, necessitating standardized test frameworks and economic viability assessments. Future research should prioritize scalable fabrication of robust sensor materials, comprehensive field validation in diverse matrices, and development of unified datasets promoting AI generalizability. Innovations in antifouling surface modifications and multimodal sensing will be critical to enhance operational stability. Cross-disciplinary collaboration and integration with emerging digital infrastructures will accelerate translation from lab prototypes to practical, regulatory-compliant monitoring tools. This pathway is essential to enable real-time, decentralized PFAS detection supporting environmental stewardship and public health protection.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Aman Kumar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Akshay Kumar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Sonam Kumari:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Nitin Kumar Singhal:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Giovanna Marrazza:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Sandeep Kumar:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Giovanna Marrazza reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe Program. Sandeep Kumar reports financial support was provided by Govt. of India. Sonam Kumari reports financial support was provided by University Grants Commission, India. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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